

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology and data catalogue and quality support

D7.20 Templates and guidance for local and central Data Privacy Impact Assessments for datasources and repository for continuous collection of completed forms and approvals

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Abstract

Started in 2019, the ConcePTION project aims to establish a large ecosystem to provide fast and reliable evidence on drug safety during pregnancy and breastfeeding. ConcePTION partners are conducting studies across Europe, some of them with the close collaboration of pregnant and breastfeeding women, which is one of the central cornerstones of the project.

As described in the research proposal, certain tasks in work packages (WP) 1 and 7 involve the active participation of several data sources through Data Access Providers (DAP) to undertake some of the tasks pre-specified in the Description of Action (DoA). In this report on deliverable D7.20, we describe the collection and public availability of the ethical documentation for participating data sources for each Data Access Provider.

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
DAP	Data Access Provider
DoA	Description of Action
IRB	Institutional Review Board
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DP	Demonstration Project
DPA	Data Processing Agreements
DAA	Data Access Agreements
DTA	Data Transfer Agreements
IC	Informed Consents
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
PIF	Patient Information Forms
UOSL	Universitetet I Oslo
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
CHUT	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse
SIDIAP	Information System for the Development of Research in Primary Care
USWAN	Swansea University
ULST	University of Ulster
MMCSA	Malformation Monitoring Centre Saxony-Anhalt
CNR-IFC	National Research Council - Institute of Clinical Physiology, Pisa
RDRU_FISABIO	Rare Disease Research Unit of The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencian Region
RTDC	Tuscany Registry of Congenital Defects
BPE	Bordeaux PharmacoEpidemiology
UNIFE	University of Ferrara

Purpose and scope of this document

One of the purposes of WP7 in the ConcePTION project is to provide ethical, governance, and quality assessment support for the conduct of distributed data collection and analyses which consequently supports the generation of high-quality real-world evidence. Task 7.10 involves collecting copies from all templates, Institutional Review Board (IRB) comments and approvals, and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical and Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) obligations.

The purpose of deliverable D7.20 is to describe the collection of documentation regarding ethical and governance approval from participating data sources in WP1 and WP7 within the ConcePTION project, with the aim to demonstrate how studies comply with current ethical and local governance requirements when using retrospective data from pregnant and breastfeeding women.

From the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA), D7.20 description is:

“Templates and guidance for local and central Data Privacy Impact Assessments for data sources and repository for continuous collection of completed forms and approvals.”

Background

ConcePTION aims to create an ecosystem for the rapid and robust generation of evidence on the safety of medications in pregnancy and lactation, using both existing and newly generated real-world data. The present report is one of the five deliverables in task 7.10 and involves our partners from WP1 and WP7.

Task 7.10 of WP7 is described as follows in the ConcePTION DoA:

“In this task we will collect copies from all templates, IRB review comments and approvals and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical (see section 5) and IMI obligations. This task will deliverable five deliverables (D7.18-7.22), providing proof and documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant.”

Work Package 1

The work of WP1 is shaped around five demonstration projects (DP), each dedicated to a disease/medication topic, for identifying data sources, developing algorithms, validating data, conducting medication utilisation studies, and conducting pregnancy outcome studies, i.e., medication safety studies (Task 1.5). Furthermore, Task 1.1 focuses on identifying data sources potentially relevant to the DP, Task 1.3 on developing algorithms to identify outcomes of interest, exposure and confounders and produce background and disease-specific prevalence rates and Task 1.4 on establishing medication utilisation for newly approved products. See ConcePTION DoA for more details.

Work Package 7

One of the purposes of WP7 is to provide quality assessment for the conduct of distributed data collection and analyses. This WP facilitates the work of WP1 and WP2 by providing support in data and analytics generation readiness. Task 7.4 and Task 7.6 are related to characterising existing data sources in the form of a catalogue and automatization of summary measures, respectively.

Task description

This deliverable report is based on the collection of documentation of ethical and governance approvals, that is – templates, informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets, participant's information sheets, Standard Operational Procedures (SOP), Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), if applicable, inter alia. The aim is to provide proof and public documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant with their ethical and local governance requirement.

The scope of this particular deliverable is ethical and governance documentation related to studies involving secondary-use of data. It is not part of this deliverable to monitor or audit whether information provision, consent procedures, and ethical approvals were conducted according to national/regional guidelines or local requirements where the studies will take place or whether they followed the recommendations from the ConcePTION consortium ([Singleton & Cunnington 2020](#)).

In 2020, we collected the information regarding ethical and governance documentation in the form of a checklist sent out to each DAP participating in WP1 and WP7. In this checklist, DAPs provided information regarding Policy documents, Governance structure for data sources, Data Processing Agreements (DPAs), Data Access Agreements (DAAs), Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs), description of approval committees, standard template protocols, study protocol, patient information forms (PIF), and informed consent forms (IC). The information collected refers to where the information is available, under which name, and who to approach to have access, thus giving a clear description of the internal procedures for each DAP.

In addition, from September 2022 to September 2023, we approached WP and DP leads via e-mail requesting further documentation, if available. [Table 1](#) shows the DAPs, the checklist, the documentation shared, and the contact person who handled the documentation until the submission of the present report. In [Table 2](#), we provided a summary of the available documentation. We expect partners to continue contributing to this 'live' report with further documentation once they receive approvals by uploading files in the corresponding repository.

Table 1. Ethical documentation

DAP	DATA SOURCE	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE DOCUMENT	CONTACT PERSON
UOSL	UOSL	<input type="radio"/> DPIA	Please address contact person for file	Hedvig Nordeng h.m.e.nordeng[at]farmasif[dot]juio[dot]no
		<input type="radio"/> DMP	Please address contact person for file	
		<input type="radio"/> IRB approval	Please address contact person for file	
IDIAP	SIDIAP	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_UiO_Norway_NH.docx	Maria Giner-Soriano mginer[at]idiapigol[dot]info
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DMP <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	Plan_ConcePTION_IDIAP_v1.0_20230110.docx 20017_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_am.docx	
USWAN	SAIL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	IGRP Approval GCRP letter -0823.pdf	Sue Jordan s.e.jordan[at]swansea[dot]ac[dot]uk
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_Wales_CN_SJ -CM 230320 INCLUDING DOCUMENTS.docx	
UNIFE	IMER	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	593-2023-Oss-UniFe.pdf	Marco Manfrini mnfmrc[at]unife[dot]it
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents-ver2.docx	
CHUT	EFEMERIS POMME	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	Letter_of_approval-Protocol-ConcePTION_signed.pdf	Christine Damase-Michel: christine.damase-michel[at]univ-tlse3[dot]fr Anna-Belle Beau Anna-belle.beau[at]univ-tlse3[dot]fr
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_EFEMERISPOMME_ABB.docx	
BPE	SNDS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_20200330revBdx RL CD.docx	Cecile Droz-Perroteau Cecile.droz[at]u-bordeaux[dot]fr
PHARMO		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checklist	200217_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents.docx	Thom Lysen thom.lysen[at]pharmo[dot]nl

FISABIO	RDRU_FISABIO	✓ Checklist	200316_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_FISABIO_updated.docx	Laia Barrachina Bonet Laia.barrachina[at]fisabio[dot]es Clara Cavero Clara.cavero[at]fisabio[dot]es
ULST		✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_JG_ML.docx	Maria Loane Ma.loane[at]ulster[dot]ac[dot]uk
AARHUS		✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_Aarhus20240108.docx	Vera Ehrenstein ve[at]clin[dot]au[dot]dk
BIPS	GePaRD	✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_BIPS.docx	Tania Schink schink[at]leibniz-bips[dot]de
CNR-IFC	RTDC	✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_Tuscany.docx	Anna Pierini Anna.pierini[at]cnr[dot]it Francesca Gorini francesca-gorini[at]cnr[dot]it
MMCSA		✓ Checklist	000_2004_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_MalfMonCent_Germany.docx	Anke Rissmann
University of Messina	CASERTA	✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_UniMe.docx	Janet Sultana jsultana[at]unime[dot]it
THL	NIHW	○ DPIA	Please address contact person for file	Maarit Leinonen Maarit.leinonen[at]thl[dot]fi
		✓ Checklist	200316_3_Checklist_Task Ethico Legal Documents_FIN.pdf	
		○ IRB approval	Please address contact person for file	

✓ Available in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

○ Not available. Contact WP lead for further information.

DAP Name	Policy document	Governance structure for data sources	DPAs	DAAs	DTAs	Description of approval committees	Standard template protocol	Study protocols	PIF	IC
UOSL	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
IDIAP	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA
USWAN	Yes	Yes	Yes	yes	No	Yes	NA	No	No	No
UNIFE	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes/No ^a	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
CHUT	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
BPE	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
PHARMO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA
FISABIO	Yes	Yes	No ^b	No ^b	No ^b	Yes	No	No	No	No
ULSTER	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
AARHUS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	No	NA	NA	NA
BIPS	Yes	No	No	No	No/Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
CNR-IFC	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
MMCSA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Eurocat NNL	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Messina	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
THL	Yes	?	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

Table 2. Overview of available documentation

DAP, data access provider; DPA, data processing agreement, DAA, data access agreement; DTA, data transfer agreement, PIF, Patient Information Forms; IC, informed consent; NA, not applicable

^a UNIFE provided only information regarding their DTA with EUROCAT. Check their checklist file for more information.

^b This document follows the guidance included in the Policy documents and follows the steps indicated in the description of the approval committees. More information can be found in their checklist file.

Availability

We proposed to make the documentation available via the [IMI-ConcePTION Member Area](#) to allow related WP leads/members to upload their documentation after the date of submission of this deliverable, if deemed necessary. We created folders named ‘Ethics deliveries’ for WP1 and WP7 in IMI-ConcePTION Member Area where we can store the related documentation presented in this report (Figure 1).

The present report will be made available as ‘Files’ in the public repository ([Zenodo – IMI ConcePTION](#)), after approval of this report. The report will be in the public domain, and available for download.

Figure 1. Example of repository for related documentation in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Documents

Work package 3 > 2- Ethics Deliverables > In vivo studies

Enter search term

Views Actions In vivo studies

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Date modified	Size
<input type="checkbox"/>	3b- AutRigMinistero[1181]Approvazione_Notifica_BDN_Forni_1181.pdf	11/10/2022 3:35 PM	454.2 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	3c- AutRigMinistero [1185]Autorizzazione_202132_Bacci_1185.pdf new.pdf	11/10/2022 3:57 PM	162.7 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	AutRigMinistero[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	8/11/2023 5:05 PM	789.0 KB

Items per Page: 10 3 items

Conclusion

The present report provides an overview of the documentation for ethical and governance approval related to the processing of personal data in large databases for studies in WP1 and WP7. Before the submission of this deliverable, several DAPs have provided the information and/or documentation stated on this report through the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area. We expect further documentation to be made available through the same media after the approval of this deliverable.

References

Singleton, P., & Cunnington, M. (2020). Report on initial information and research governance for WP1-5 (D7.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840292>